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EVOLUTION OF COMMUNICATION METHODS OVER THE PAST 10 YEARS

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We live in a world where more than 1.65 billion active Internet users. This phenomenon equally affects ordinary users and companies. Together we will look at why social networks developed in a short time and how they turned into a storm, an overlooking world.

The first website of a social network, that overcame million active users in a month, was MySpace, and he attained this border approximately in 2004, and it is possible to say that this beginning of social networks, what we know them today.

Then large social networks that existed 10 and more than years began to appear, such as Facebook, YouTube, WhatsApp, WeChat, Instagram, Snapchat, and Reddit, and other websites and appendixes began widely and quickly to spread whenever a new idea appeared.

For example, TikTok started in September 2016, and to the middle of 2018 a year, the number of users already attained semi-milliard. It specifies that for this period Tik Tok collected on average about 20 million FTUS in a month.

This first point became the result of the huge force of the Internet. With such platforms, as social networks, you can suddenly remain in connection with friends that did not intermingle a long ago, meet with new people and do all of it, keeping indoors from your own home.

Another key aspect that does social networks such success is their design. In respect of user interface, nothing to have a look at with these platforms. For example, Facebook can use each, from teenagers to the grandmothers and grand-dads.

The word "free of charge" is a very powerful instrument in the world of the Internet. People at once will make an effort to try anything, if it is free of charge, these platforms are so successful, therefore. He gives all these remarkable functions and possibilities of connection without a necessity to pay for these excellent services.

Social networks are beyond simple conversation and images. Such networks, like LinkedIn, give a professional platform that helps companies and competitors to work. It released them from a necessity to search the excellent impressions, and people could take advantage of present employment opportunities.

Marketing in social networks is important now for good reason. These platforms give a possibility to distribute the brand and products on the Internet to the companies. Some companies also took advantage of this, to intermingle with the clients over the Internet and quickly to work out problems.

Most countries use social networks according to a global web index, the Philippines head the list of the duration of the use, where a user conducts in social networks on the average 4 hours and minute in a day, then Nigeria 3 hours 36 minutes, and then India 2 hours 25 minutes. While in the developed countries, such as the USA, Great Britain, Germany and Japan, the speed of the use makes only 45 minutes.

In respect of stake of users for the young age-related group, then a list is headed by the rich European countries, for example, for the age-related group of 16-24, the percent of users makes 97,2% in Iceland, 96,5% in Hungary, 96% in Sweden, 95,3% in Portugal and 94,7% and 94,5% in Norway and Denmark accordingly.

The new pandemic of the virus of crown changed the world look at the beginning of 2020 and compelled hundreds of millions of people to remain in the houses all over the world within the framework of the commandant hour entered by the governments of most countries for the citizens all over the world. in an attempt to restrain the distribution of the virus.

Here social networks played an important role, helping most people observe new laws. He also plays a fundamental role distribution of information and fights against widely spreading rumors, distinguishing the special corner for news and instructions from reliable sources, such as the Worldwide organization of health protection, and passing to them the users.

All companies intensively work and add large efforts for the development of social networks that they give to the users. We have heard much news of the development of technology of virtual reality and integration of her with these services. Not to mention the use of artificial intelligence, to hear about behavior users and to give recommendations to them. But we do not know, as far as these technologies will reach in the future.